

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

Check it out! More than 140 Edible City Solutions from "sister" project H2020 NATURAVATION already available on the EdiCitNet toolbox web

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

WP2 is very happy to announce that we have been collaborating with H2020 "sister" project NATURVATION in order to integrate the edible Nature-Based Solutions from NATURVATION ATLAS (<https://naturvation.eu/atlas>) into the EdiCitNet catalogue (available on (<https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/>)).

As a result of this collaboration, on the EdiCitNet catalogue, you will find information about more than 140 ECS from NATURVATION project, including a detailed description, starting year, type of funding, social medias, webs and related documents (PDF). For more information you can access the original source (NATURVATION ATLAS).

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

3ff1797f-42cc-4295-8bc7-8a11b78af269/MicrosoftTeams-image__2_.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

<https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/>

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

08/12/2020

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Joana Castellar

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

Institut Català de Recerca de l'Aigua (ICRA)

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Research technician

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

Girona, Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jcastellar@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
 No, none of them
 Only on Twitter
 Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

puerta@arttic.eu